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Enhancing Student Performance in Bread and Pastry Production through Brochure-Based Learning among Grade 11 Home Economics Majors

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ABSTRACT

This action research examined the effectiveness of a crafted Brochure-based Learning Material in enhancing the performance of Grade 11 learners specializing in Bread and Pastry Production at Don Eufemio F. Eriguel Memorial National High School. Addressing the challenges of limited resources and an unfavorable teacher-student ratio, the study aimed to develop, validate, and implement a structured instructional material to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Using an experimental research design, 40 learners were randomly assigned to control and experimental groups. Both groups undertook pretests and posttests, but only the experimental group utilized the Brochure-based Learning. Research instruments included a validated 60-item multiple-choice test and the Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) Evaluation Rating Sheet for Printed Materials. Expert evaluators assessed the brochure-based learning in terms of content, format, presentation, organization, and accuracy. Findings revealed that the brochure-based learning was highly rated across all evaluation criteria, confirming its validity and reliability as an instructional resource. Performance results showed that while both groups improved from pretest to posttest, the experimental group demonstrated significantly higher gains in mean percentage scores, with several learners achieving "Outstanding" proficiency levels. Statistical analysis further established a significant difference between the two groups, affirming the handbook's effectiveness in improving learning outcomes. The study concludes that the crafted brochure-based learning effectively enhances student performance by providing structured guidance, practical applications, and accessible learning support. It recommends continuous refinement of the brochure-based learning, longitudinal evaluation of its impact, integration into other Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) programs, and teacher training for effective utilization. This research underscores the value of well-designed instructional resources in strengthening technical-vocational education and preparing learners for industry-relevant competencies.

Keywords: *Brochure-Based Learning, Technical-Vocational Education, Bread and Pastry Production, Instructional Materials, Student Performance*

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